

Women and Computing

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Abstract

The contribution of women had been tremendous in all possible walks of life. And the field of computing had been no exception. This paper focuses on the role and contributions of women in computing starting from the earliest recorded history till date. And also takes a look at the global mind set on gender disparity in the field of computing. The observation made is that the percentage of women in the field of Information Technology (IT) is not globally uniform. But in countries like India, the percentage of women are more in career and in opting for higher education in IT. The role of women does consume a chunk to decide and design the global future in the field of computing.

Introduction

The gender issues are as old as the earth itself and starts from the days of Adam and Eve. Still it remains to be an issue and there seems to be never an end. Beyond all these issues, the contribution of women had been tremendous in all possible walks of life. And the field of computing had been no exception. It has seen mind boggling and heartwarming contributions by women. This paper brings forth the contributions of women in computing down the ages and discusses the current trend in computing with the mind set of young women across the globe in deciding their field of interest in higher education and in their choice of career paths.

Women in Computing Down the Ages

The earliest recorded information regarding various computations being done by women dates back to the 1700s. It was Lepaute who worked in the team, along with men, that predicted the date of return of Halley's Comet. After that in 1800s Ada Lovelace, daughter of the great poet Lord Byron, was the first woman and the first person to publish an algorithm intended to be executed by the first modern computer, the Analytical Engine, created by Charles Babbage. She is regarded as the first computer programmer and the Mother of Programming. In 1875 Anna Winlock became a computer for the Harvard Observatory to work for 25 cents an hour. By 1880, Edward Charles Pickering had hired several women to work for him at Harvard because he felt that women could do the job as well as men and he could ask them to volunteer or work for less pay.

After this great beginning by women, a big list of women who themselves were like computers, the human computers, contributed

their might in computing. The list of women seems to be infinite. In 1900 starting from World War – I the women have played remarkable role in various engineering fields involving computing like astronomy, space research, telephone and telegraph, bio-medical sciences to name a few. During World War II, in 1942, Hedy Lamarr invented the frequency-hopping technology that later paved way for the invention of wireless signals like Wi-Fi and Bluetooth 2. During 1940s Grace Hopper is one prominent name amidst many. Grace Hopper was both intelligent and brave. She served the Navy as the Rear Admiral. Along side she contributed to the field of Computer Science. She was the first person to create a compiler for a programming language and also is the Mother of COBOL language. Apart from major contributions like Algorithms, Languages and Compilers even very simple things like terminologies used in computing like the word “Bug” and “Debug” was coined by women and the credit goes to Grace Hopper again. Rear Admiral Grace Brewster Murray Hopper was responsible not only for the development of the Cobol language but also to make computers and computing more accessible and to bring the research and career interests of women in computing to the forefront³. She programmed the BINAC - a small binary machine built in secret for the Snark Missile project. At that time she seems to have realized that the computer was a symbol manipulator and not just a big calculator. This thought of her’s have paved way for the technological development that the computing world is experiencing. Again the brain behind was a woman.

The Association for Computing Machinery Turing Award, referred to as the “Nobel Prize” of computing, was named in honor of Alan Turing. This prestigious award has been won by three women between 1966 and 20184. All three of them are after 2000.

- 2006 – Francis “Fran” Elizabeth Allen For pioneering contributions to the theory and practice of optimizing compiler techniques that laid the foundation for modern optimizing compilers and automatic parallel execution⁵.
- 2008 – Barbara Liskov For contributions to practical and theoretical foundations of programming language and system design, especially related to data abstraction, fault tolerance, and distributed computing⁶.
- 2012 – Shafi Goldwasser Along with Silvio Micali, for transformative work that laid the complexity-theoretic foundations for the science of cryptography, and in the process pioneered new methods for efficient verification of mathematical proofs in complexity theory⁷.

The British Computer Society Information Retrieval Specialist Group in conjunction with the British Computer Society created an award in 2008 to commemorate the achievements of Karen Spärck Jones (KSJ), a Professor Emerita of Computers and Information at the University of Cambridge and one of the most remarkable woman in computer science. The KSJ award has been won by four women between 2009 and 2017:

- 2009 – Mirella Lapata
- 2012 – Diane Kelly
- 2015 – Emine Yilmaz
- 2016 – Jaime Teevan

In 2017, Michelle Simmons founded the first quantum computing company in Australia. The team, which has made “great strides” in 2018, plans to develop a 10-qubit prototype silicon quantum integrated circuit by 2022. Also in 2017, Doina Precup became the head of Deep Mind Montreal, working on artificial intelligence.

These are clear indicators that women are still contributing their might in the field of computing.

Gender Gap in Computing

Though the women had immense contributions to the field of computing, all along tagged the gender issues too. The global observation made is that the percentage of women in the Information Technology field are less compared to their male counterparts. In the 21st century, several attempts have been made to reduce the gender disparity in IT and get more women involved in computing. A 2001 survey found that while both sexes use computers and the internet in equal measure, women were still five times less likely to choose it as a career or study the subject beyond standard secondary education. In 2004, the National Centre for Women & Information Technology was established by Lucy Sanders to address the gender gap. Despite the pioneering work of some designers, video games are still considered biased towards men. A 2013 survey by the International Game Developers Association revealed only 22% of game designers are women.

One of the biggest problems facing women in computing in the modern era is that they often find themselves working in an environment that is largely unpleasant, so they don't stay on in the careers in programming and technology. In 2013, a National Public Radio report said 20% of computer programmers in the US are female. In 2017, James Damore was fired from Google after claiming there was a biological reason for a lack of female computer scientists. The following year, Wikipedia was criticised for not having an article about scientist Donna Strickland until shortly after she won the Nobel Prize for Physics, which was attributed to a severe gender disparity of the site's editors.

In 1991, Massachusetts Institute of Technology undergraduate Ellen Spertus wrote an essay "Why Are There So Few Women in Computer Science?", which complained about inherent sexism in IT, which was responsible for a lack of women in computing. The University of Southampton's Wendy Hall has said the attractiveness of computers to women decreased significantly in the 1980s when they "were sold as toys for boys", and believes the cultural stigma has remained ever since, and may even be getting worse. Kathleen Lehman, project manager of the BRAID Initiative at UCLA has said a problem is that typically women aim for perfection and feel disillusioned when code does not compile, whereas men may simply treat it as a learning experience. The gender disparity in IT is not global. The ratio of female to male computer scientists is significantly higher in India compared to the West. The number of women in specialist IT roles in India is significantly higher than in the UK. The study, in partnership with Indian IT trade association firm Nasscom, of IT professionals and middle management from companies in the UK and India, found 35% of people with specialist technology roles in India are women, compared to 17% in the UK⁸. In Europe, Bulgaria and Romania have the highest rates of women going into computer programming. In government universities in Saudi Arabia in 2014, Arab women made up 59% of students enrolled in computer science.

Even though both genders are equally talented in logic and problem solving, parents create the initial divide. Boys were given computers more often than girls. This made them more comfortable when teachers started using computers in the classroom. The basic attitude towards facing problems are different among genders, where women have a tendency to want to avoid mistakes and may be frustrated when their code does not work, on the other hand, men consider programming as a trial-and-error process⁹.

Conclusion

In certain countries the percentage of women in technology are more and some others they are less. But on the whole the percentage of women compared to men seems to be less except in few countries. India context seems to very promising, where women performing is more. Whichever the country there seems to be no general consensus for any key reason for there being less women

in computing. It has been observed that there is a greater gap in countries where people of both sexes are treated more equally, contradicting any theories that society in general is to blame for any disparity. A report in the Daily Telegraph suggested that women generally prefer people-facing jobs, which many computing and IT positions do not have, while men prefer jobs geared towards objects and tasks. When seeking solutions for women's low participation in computing, it is important to consider all cultural and societal factors that may affect this participation. The solution identified for one country may not be suitable for another country¹⁰.

In Indian context, though the percentage is more in comparison to other countries, still the number can be still more. For this to be achieved the role of Parents and Teachers are very crucial. Parents should avoid creating the initial divide at home and instil similar traits in children beyond gender. With the strong foundation laid at home, children when they venture to the outside world Teachers will be the next stage of influence. Teachers have a large influence on students' decision to study computer science and as a career. Students who receive positive reinforcement are three times more likely to go into computer science. Therefore, the role of parents and teachers are immense in controlling the gender disparities and to motivate more women to enter the field of computing.

Women had been and will be playing their role in the field of computing and the future of computing will be coalesced with women in it.

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